

Survey of Digital Storytelling Initiatives across the Global South

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Overview

The NEH-AHRC project on digital storytelling explored how to best empower secondary school and university educators and learners in South Africa and Botswana to explore cultural heritage through a digital archive called *metsemegologolo* (<https://www.metsemegologolo.org.za>). *Metsemegologolo*, ‘ancient towns’ in Setswana (<https://www.metsemegologolo.org.za>), is an open-source prototype database containing archaeological data, heritage objects, historical maps, oral histories and poetry about precolonial African urbanisms. The NEH/AHRC project focused especially on how to best mobilize the *metsemegologolo* archive for digital storytelling within resource-limited educational environments.

As part of the background research associated with the grant, the project team evaluated other heritage digital archives and storytelling platforms across the Global South for similarities and differences, and for potential future directions for *metsemegologolo*. Given the broadness of the topics of digital storytelling and Global South, the team thought it was best to first search for and highlight those based on African and on African history and archaeology, and/or that engage with African museum objects. However, good comparatives were more limited than we initially hoped, especially at the extent and with the types of data that were of interest to our *metsemegologolo* collaborators, we broadened our considerations to include marginalized and/or difficult histories, such as those of the African American and other minorities’ experiences in the United States. This proved especially productive for generating additional comparative content and, as described below, became the focus on the survey results. Comparative projects were categorized both based on the type of web resource (archive, exhibit, storytelling), the geographic region it involved, and whether the curated materials were archaeological, historical, or ethnographic in nature. Emphasis on websites that were engaging with digitized material beyond documents, especially with spatial and/or 3D data, helped sort through potential comparatives. The final list of 27 projects we reviewed is not comprehensive, but relatively representative of the breadth of approaches to archival and archaeological materials.

Name	Website	Type	Region	Period	Institution
Emandulo	http://emandulo.apc.uct.ac.za/	Archive	Africa (south)	Hist	UCT

The Digital Bleek and Lloyd	http://loydbleekcollection.cs.uct.ac.za/	Archive	Africa (south)	Hist	UCT
Five Hundred Year Archive	https://fhya.org/	Archive	Africa (south)	Arch	UCT
African Digital Heritage	https://africandigitalheritage.org/	Exhibit	Africa (east)	Ethno	NPO
Horn Heritage	https://www.hornheritage.org/	Exhibit	Africa (east)	Ethno	NPO
CyArk	https://www.cyark.org/	Exhibit	Mult	Mult	NPO
Virtual Karam	http://history.usf.edu/idex/VKC.html	Exhibit	Middle East	Arch	USF
Pan-African Digital Museum	https://pahmuseum.org/	Exhibit	Africa (mult)	Ethno	NPO
Rising Above	https://risingabove.cast.uark.edu/	Mult	USA	Hist	UArk
Historic Little Rock	https://hlr.cast.uark.edu/	Mult	USA	Hist	UArk
Montpellier	https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/faadff77aad54b67b4fc5d9f659f2baa	Mult	USA	Arch	NPO
Hampson Virtual Museum	https://hampson.cast.uark.edu/	Exhibit	USA	Arch	UArk
African Rock Art	https://africanrockart.britishmuseum.org/thematic/rockartvr/	Exhibit	Africa (mult)	Arch	British Museum
Infinite Armenias	https://projects.cah.ucf.edu/infinitearmenias/	Story	Europe	Arch	UCF
MyEleusis	https://myeleusis.com/	Mult	Europe	Arch	EU
Finding the Forgotten Graduate	https://www.pps.co.za/fg/desktop/	Story	Africa (south)	Hist	FPO
Bailey's African History Archive	https://www.baha.co.za/about/	Archive	Africa (mult)	Hist	NPO
African Archaeology Archive Cologne	https://arachne.dainst.org/project/afrarchcologne	Archive	Africa (mult)	Arch	AAArC/UoC
Afriterra Cartographic Library	https://afriterra.org/	Archive	Africa (mul)	Hist	NPO
Sustainable African Cities	https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/71e3d363de12412badff8010674bd427	Story	Africa (mult)	Ethno	EuC

Archives Africa	https://archives-africa.org/	Archive	Africa (mult)	History	KCL
African Conservation Story Maps	https://storymaps.arcgis.com/collections/0a0552b4f088490198b217d330e1a081	Story	Africa (mult)	Ethno	Various/ESRI
Indian Ocean in World History	https://www.indianoceanhistory.org/	Story	Africa (east)	Hist	SQCC
Virtual Rosewood	https://www.virtualrosewood.com	Story	USA	Arch	UTRGV
Keweenaw Time Traveler	www.mapyourhistory.org	Story	USA	Arch	MTU
CCC @ Devils Den State Park	http://ccc.cast.uark.edu/	Archive	USA	Hist	UArk
St. Mark's Memory Mapping Project	https://www.districtsix.co.za/project/st-marks-memory-mapping-project/	Story	Africa (south)	Hist	UMich

Not represented here, but many of the African archival and storytelling websites seem to be focused on either post-independence politics (e.g., the struggle against Apartheid), colonialism, and/or the transatlantic slave trade. There seemed a major gap – and a real need – for quality, educational resources about the African precolonial period, the emphasis of our partner project.

The survey results and the featured project, *Rising Above*, helped guide conversation at the NEH-AHRC workshop that was held in Cambridge in September 2022. The survey also provided a rich source for inviting speakers for the NEH-AHRC webinar held in March 2023 (recording available at <https://www.metsemegologolo.org.za/wordpress/digital-storytelling/neh-ahrc-digital-storytelling-webinar/>). Further, there appeared a need to engage with a wider set of materials beyond the written archive. Within African history, it is known that the comparative paucity of written documents, especially written by Africans from an African perspective, has skewed interpretations of historical encounters, reinforcing (even if indirectly and unintentionally) the viewpoints of white, male, colonial powers. Within African studies, this led to the development of placing oral histories on par with the written record (e.g., Vansina 1961). A similar foundational movement within historical archaeology (e.g., Ferguson 1977) and the humanities (e.g., Prown 1982) helped to posit material cultural analysis as a complementary, and at times contradictory, source of information providing insights about human behavior. Those movements have continued to mature and grow into the digital space.

Given *metsemegologolo's* emphasis on a range of spatial and non-spatial data, and the desire for a relationship database, the NEH-AHRC team thought it best to narrow in on the *Rising Above* database and storytelling website, which focuses on the history of Japanese-American internment in Arkansas during World War II. Although the location lies outside of the Global South, the

content and structure generated the greatest source for conversation, comparison, and inspiration. The remainder of this report provides a summary of Rising Above, a fully-fledged project that involves the archaeological and historical records broadly across a wide set of materials, including spatial and visual components; that desire a relational database; and that promote a marginalized and difficult histories that become relatable to an interested public.

The Rising Above Project

Rising Above in Arkansas is a digital storytelling website and archive that tells the story of Japanese American incarceration in Arkansas during WWII. It is the result of a multi-year collaboration involving specialists in history, landscape architecture, and technology and contributions from eight archives throughout the state. The purpose of the project was to centralize the wealth of material documentation in Arkansas institutions related to both the Rohwer and Jerome camps and to capitalize on the expertise of the project participants to present this information in a novel and interesting way. The resulting website is divided into four principal areas: an interactive series of maps, a digital archive with connections graph, a timeline, and the 3D reconstruction of a barrack's block. Each component of the site presents a part of the story about Japanese Incarceration during the war.

Users are encouraged to start with the Maps page which feature a spatially driven interface focused on the camp years from 1942 to 1945. The maps are organized into six themes, each with multiple subthemes, that illustrate the forced removal of Japanese Americans from their home, the design/construction of the camps, life in camp, and leaving camp. An historical narrative in the left sidebar guides the user through the maps and additional information and supporting media are available when map features are selected. With this drill-down approach, more information is provided to the user the more that they interact with the maps. While interactive maps can be time consuming to develop, they present a unique opportunity for storytelling that unites spatial context, exploration, and a variety of media sources. Maps provide a multi-faceted approach for learning about a place or an event and can provide unique learning experiences based on the level of user engagement and participation.

The Rising Above maps are created using Openlayers, an open-source JavaScript library for displaying maps on web pages, with a CodeIgniter (PHP-based) framework and MySQL database. The maps reside on local servers with other similar projects and applications that have a dedicated support staff to keep them maintained and functioning into the future. While a custom solution is advantageous for providing complete control over the final product, it requires specially trained staff for development and continued upkeep. Other similar out-of-the-box solutions, such as ESRI Storymaps and Omeka, produce results that are similar to the Rising Above maps. They remove the need for highly skilled developers by providing relatively advanced, yet easy-to-use tools for map creation and material integration but often with limited customization. They also likely do not require continued upkeep by project staff as the data/maps are often maintained by the provider. Choosing the right online mapping solution should be determined largely by the technical proficiencies of the project team and the immediate as well as long-term goals of the project. All of the mapping solutions listed here

should perform equally well in limited bandwidth environments however this should be tested before implementation.

The next component of the site, the Rising Above Archive contains nearly 2,500 items from the Rohwer and Jerome camps including artwork, correspondences, local newspaper articles, incarcerated autobiographies and more. Each item provides a unique insight into camp life and features full metadata. Metadata is critical for providing contextual information and searchability. Users are able to query items in the archive by item type, date, camp, collection name, topic, individual names, and more. The date field is particularly valuable as there's over 100 years' worth of materials in the archive. While the camps only operated for three years from 1942-1945, there are numerous items from before and after the camps closing that are relevant to the story of incarceration and how it transformed the lives of many people. For example, querying the database to view items from 1945-1960 reveals letters exchanged between former incarcerated and administrators evidencing friendships that persisted well beyond the war years, photos of former incarcerated in their new homes after camp, and government documents indicating the sale of camp land. It should be noted that exact dates are not always available for historic documents however using a date window (*circa + a date range*) is valuable for placing a document in its correct temporal context and in turn, useful for the end user.

In addition to date, the ability to search by topic is important for querying the archive for specific subjects of interest. While curating subjects or keyword lists can be a time-consuming task, it is important for making key concepts easily accessible to users. For the Rising Above archive, the team reached out to another archival group, DENSHO, to request use of their curated list of topics. This not only saved the project team time from having to curate their own list but also provides consistency across multiple archives dedicated to the topic of Japanese American incarceration. Like many of the metadata entries in the Rising Above archive, a user can query the archive using the Filters button located at the top of the page or if they are on a specific entry and they would like to see more items that share the same topic, they can simply click on the topic or any other hyperlinked metadata from the item's metadata list. Having multiple routes for exploration and discovery is valuable in a digital archive.

One of the unique metadata fields, the Names field allows users to filter items in the archive related to a specific individual. Preserving names maintains a human connection to the archival items and reveals social connections between people. While the user can filter the archive based on an individual's name, the Connections graphs for Rohwer and Jerome, provide a visual representation of these social connections at each camp. Each graph selects and displays all of the archival items from each camp, color coded by item type and the individuals referenced by those items. The size of each node in the graph is proportionate to the number of connections it has. Therefore, individuals that have a lot of items associated with them or conversely, items that reference a lot of individuals (i.e. yearbooks, newspaper articles, etc..) will be displayed with a larger node. When a user hovers over the name of an individual or an archival item in the graph, all of the connections to the person or item are highlighted. The graph is naturally clustered into groups of individuals with shared mutual connections to archival items. It

provides a quick visual assessment of who-knows-who based on their proximity to one another and to the archival items that connect them.

While this is a novel way to view historical social connections, there are a couple of noted shortcomings. First, the individuals in the Rising Above Connections graphs with a high degree of connectivity are camp administrators whose collections have been preserved in the project. So, there is a source-bias towards administrators rather than the incarcerated population whose story is the primary focus of the project. Second, if an item in the archive has not been associated with either the Jerome or the Rohwer camp then it is not displayed in either Connections graph. The project team chose to separate the items in the archive based on camp due to data volume. With nearly 2,500 items in the archive referencing over 6,500 individuals, it was ineffective to view everything simultaneously. A 9,000 node graph revealed little visual hierarchy and spatial organization. Therefore, in datasets with potentially thousands of nodes, it is likely necessary to subset the data in some way. Even with the identified shortcomings, the Rising Above Connections graphs provide an interesting visual toolkit for exploring social networks in historical archives.

Finally, the Rising Above archive provides full transcriptions for all text documents. Searchable transcriptions allow users to query the archive using terms that may not be preserved in other metadata fields. If full transcriptions are not possible, it is generally recommended to at least provide a brief description of the text content. Again, the primary objective for any historical archive should be accessibility by the end user.

Other components on the Rising Above website include a timeline and an interactive, 3D reconstruction of a barracks' block. The timeline includes over 150 years of history and covers key events leading up to and following the incarceration period. It is generalized and provides much needed context to understanding why Japanese Americans were incarcerated during WWII and also what happened after the camps closed. The last component of the site, the 3D reconstruction, provides an immersive, walk-through focused on the physical and social characteristics of a residential block at Rohwer. Much like the maps it is focused on portraying what life was like in camp but at the scale of the residential block. Both the timeline and 3D reconstruction include primary sourced documents, videos, and other archival items from the Rising Above archive and other archives relating to Japanese American incarceration during WWII.

The Rising Above website uses a variety of innovative and informative tools for telling the history of the Japanese American incarceration in Arkansas. The site is custom programmed using a variety of open source and low cost solutions and should likely perform well in environments with low bandwidth. Users are provided with multiple paths for learning and discovery and the site is particularly effective for engaging K-12 users.

When considering environments with limited bandwidth, a limitation might likely come from media file sizes. When preparing media for these environments, a file size threshold per media type should be tested and predetermined. It would be advantageous for end users to have multiple file resolutions available to them, allowing them to choose an appropriate resolution

based on their connection speed. This applies to all media on a site including images, video, audio, 3D objects, and more that might be included in an archive, supporting files for interactive maps, timelines, or other site features. Aerial imagery on maps can be particularly cumbersome and time intensive to load and should be left off by default with the option for turning on as resources allow.

References

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